

EFFECTIVENESS AND CHALLENGES OF TIME MANAGEMENT STRATEGIES IN BALANCING ACADEMICS AND ATHLETICS AMONG STUDENT-ATHLETES

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ABSTRACT

This study aimed to determine the effectiveness and challenges of time management strategies among student-athletes in balancing their academic and athletic responsibilities. Using descriptive quantitative research design and total enumeration sampling, 30 junior high, senior high, and college student-athletes from one of the private institutions in Sariaya, Quezon, were surveyed. The results showed that among the strategies, goal setting (WAM = 3.64) was the highest in effectiveness, followed by task prioritization (WAM = 3.63) and scheduling and planning (WAM = 3.59). All of these variables got a qualitative index of Strongly Agree. For challenges, the most significant was athletic training and competition schedules (WAM = 3.17), followed by academic workload and deadlines (WAM = 3.01), and time conflicts between academics and athletics (WAM = 2.89). All of these variables got a qualitative index of Agree. Scheduling and planning were the least effective time management strategies commonly used by the respondents. On the other hand, the most challenging is the athletic training and competition schedules. As an output, the researchers suggested a time-management strategies presented in an informational brochure entitled "Smart Time Management Strategies: A Student-Athlete's Guide to Effective Time Management," which provides practical strategies such as SMART goal setting, proactive planning, and balancing techniques to enhance the effectiveness and minimize challenges in balancing academic and athletic responsibilities of the student-athletes.

Keywords: *time management, student-athletes, goal setting, task prioritization, scheduling, academic-athletic balance, challenge*

INTRODUCTION

Student-athletes face unique challenges as they are required to perform effectively in both academic and athletic domains. Balancing coursework, examinations, and academic requirements alongside rigorous training schedules, competitions, and physical conditioning often places student-athletes under significant pressure. Effective time management has therefore become an essential skill that enables student-athletes to meet these dual demands while maintaining satisfactory academic performance and athletic achievement.

Time management refers to the ability to plan, organize, prioritize, and allocate time efficiently to accomplish specific tasks and goals. In the context of student-athletes, effective time management allows individuals to balance academic responsibilities with athletic commitments while minimizing stress and role conflict. According to McCombes (2019), descriptive research highlights how individuals manage tasks and responsibilities within specific contexts, making it an appropriate approach to examining the time management practices of student-athletes. Studies have shown that students who effectively manage their time tend to demonstrate better academic outcomes, reduced stress levels, and improved overall well-being.

Several theories support the importance of time management in understanding student-athletes' experiences. McClelland's Learned Needs Theory emphasizes the role of achievement motivation in goal-directed behavior, suggesting that student-athletes with strong achievement needs are more likely to adopt effective goal-setting and planning strategies. Additionally, the Pickle Jar Theory of time management highlights the importance of prioritization, emphasizing that critical tasks must be addressed before less important activities. Goode's Role Strain Theory further explains how individuals experience stress when managing multiple roles simultaneously, a common situation for student-athletes who must fulfill academic and athletic expectations.

Despite the recognized importance of time management, many student-athletes continue to experience challenges such as academic workload pressure, overlapping schedules, fatigue, and limited recovery time. Previous studies have noted that intensive training and competition schedules may negatively affect academic engagement and performance if not managed properly (Magdato, 2021). Similarly, task prioritization difficulties and conflicting deadlines often contribute to stress and reduced academic focus (Middleton et al., 2018).

In the Philippine higher education context, limited local research has focused specifically on the effectiveness of time management strategies and the challenges faced by student-athletes in balancing academics and athletics. This gap highlights the need for empirical studies that examine how student-athletes manage their time and identify

factors that hinder or support their dual roles. Addressing this gap is important in developing evidence-based strategies that promote both academic success and athletic performance.

Thus, this study aims to determine the effectiveness of time management strategies employed by student-athletes and to identify the challenges they encounter in balancing academic and athletic responsibilities. The findings of this study are expected to contribute to existing literature and serve as a basis for designing practical time management strategies that may help student-athletes manage their responsibilities more effectively.

Research Questions

This study aimed to determine the effectiveness and challenges of time management strategies and the challenges encountered by student-athletes in balancing their academic and athletic responsibilities. This study aimed to answer the following questions:

1. What time management strategies are commonly used by student-athletes in balancing their academics and athletics in terms of:
 - 1.1 scheduling and planning;
 - 1.2 task prioritization; and
 - 1.3 goal setting?
2. What challenges in time management strategies are faced by student-athletes in managing their academics and athletics in terms of:
 - 2.1 academic workload and deadlines;
 - 2.2 athletic training and competition schedules; and
 - 2.3 time conflicts between academic and athletic responsibilities?
3. Based on the research findings, what informative material can be suggested by the researchers to enhance the effectiveness and minimize challenges in balancing the academic and athletic responsibilities of the respondents?

METHODOLOGY

Research Design

This study utilized a descriptive research design in a quantitative approach to determine the effectiveness and challenges of time management strategies in balancing academics and athletics among student-athletes. The objective is to identify and describe the time management strategies used by student-athletes, and to determine how these strategies support or hinder their performance in both academic and athletic areas.

According to McCombes (2019), descriptive research is a type of research method that aims to systematically describe a phenomenon, population, or situation without manipulating variables. It focuses on answering the "what" rather than the "why" by

gathering information through surveys, observations, case studies, and other qualitative or quantitative approaches.

This research design was chosen since the study aimed to describe the current situation of student-athletes, specifically their time management strategies and the challenges they experience. It helped present real experiences and actual situations based on the data gathered from the participants.

Research Locale

The study was conducted in one private educational institution located in Sariaya, Quezon. The institution accommodates a wide range of student-athletes across various educational levels, all of whom are engaged in both academic and athletic responsibilities. Initial observations and informal feedback from school personnel and students suggest the presence of time-related challenges among student-athletes. These include difficulties in balancing study schedules with training sessions, meeting academic deadlines, and maintaining consistent performance in both areas. Such concerns highlight the relevance and urgency of the study in this specific setting.

The selection of this locale provides a comprehensive environment for determining how student-athletes from junior high to college manage their time. It allowed the researchers to analyze the effectiveness and challenges of time management strategies across developmental stages and academic expectations, thereby enriching the scope and depth of the study.

Respondents and Sampling Technique

The total population for this study consists of junior high, senior high, and college student-athletes enrolled in one private institution during the Academic Year 2024–2025. These student-athletes are actively engaged in both academic activities and organized sports within the institution. Their consistent participation in athletic events and maintenance of academic responsibilities make them appropriate subjects for a study on time management strategies.

This study employed a total enumeration sampling technique, a non-probability sampling method wherein participants are selected based on specific characteristics aligned with the study's objectives. Total Population Sampling | Lærd Dissertation, total population sampling is a type of purposive sampling technique that involves examining the entire population (i.e., the total population) that has a particular set of characteristics (e.g., specific attributes/traits, experience, knowledge, skills, exposure to an event, etc.). Whilst total population sampling is infrequently used, there are specific types of research where total population sampling can be very useful. This article (a) explains what total population sampling is and when it may be appropriate to use it, (b) sets out some examples of total population sampling, (c) shows how to create a total population sample, and (d) discusses the advantages and disadvantages of total population sampling.

A total of 30 student-athletes from various academic levels were selected to

participate in the study. These respondents were invited to answer a researcher-made questionnaire on a scheduled date and time, allowing for consistent and accurate data collection regarding the effectiveness and challenges of time management strategies in balancing academics and athletics.

Data Gathering Procedure

The researchers have used various procedures to gather the necessary data for the study. After the questionnaire was examined and validated, the researchers sought approval from their advisers and the subject teachers. Once approved, the researchers requested permission from the school principal to collect the needed data. The researchers assured the principal that the data gathered would only be used for the study and would not be shared or leaked anywhere. After receiving the principal's approval, the researchers proceeded with the data collection.

The survey questionnaires were distributed both through Google Forms and printed copies to the Junior High, Senior High, and College students who met the set criteria for respondents. The researchers visited each classroom of the respondents, ensuring they explained the purpose of the study and asked for their approval and cooperation. The data gathering took three weeks to accomplish.

Research Instrument

The researchers used a self-made survey checklist questionnaire to determine the effectiveness and challenges of time management strategies in balancing academics and athletics among student-athletes.

The questionnaire is comprised of two parts. The first part was used to determine the effective time management strategies commonly used by the respondents in balancing their academics and athletics in terms of scheduling and planning, task prioritization, and goal setting. While the second part determined the challenges in time management strategies faced by the respondents in managing their academics and athletics in terms of: academic workload and deadlines, athletic training and competition schedules, and time conflicts between academics and athletics.

Each variable contains five statements, for a total of thirty statements. Likert scale to guide the respondents in rating the statements: 4 if the respondents Strongly Agree (SA), 3 if Agree (A), 2 if Disagree (D), and 1 if Strongly Disagree (SD).

Statistical Treatment of Data

The researchers used the following statistical treatment to analyze the data gathered precisely.

To determine both the effective time management strategies commonly used by student-athletes in balancing their academic and athletic responsibilities and the challenges they face in time management, the researchers will utilize the Weighted

Arithmetic Mean (WAM) as the statistical treatment. The formula is as follows.
Formula:

$$W = \frac{\sum_{i=1}^n W_i X_i}{\sum_{i=1}^n W_i}$$

Where:

W= Weighted Average

n= Numbers of Terms to be Average

Wi= Corresponding Weight

Xi= Value of any particular

The researchers used a *4- Point Likert scale* and interpreted the result using the continuous scale below.

Point Scale	Mean Range	Verbal Interpretation
4	3.26 - 4.00	Strongly Agree
3	2.51 - 3.25	Agree
2	1.76 - 2.50	Disagree
1	1.00 - 1.75	Strongly Disagree

Scope and Limitations

This study determined the effectiveness of time management strategies among student-athletes and identifies the challenges they encounter in balancing their academic and athletic responsibilities. The research specifically determined senior high school student-athletes from one secondary private institution in Sariaya, Quezon. The key variables for the strategies include scheduling and planning, task prioritization, and goal setting while for challenges encountered in balancing academic and athletic responsibilities as part of the time management process includes academic workload and deadlines, athletic training and competition schedules, and time conflicts between academics and athletics. The study employed a descriptive quantitative research design, using a self-made survey checklist questionnaire to gather data. To analyze the responses, the weighted arithmetic mean was utilized. This study also employed a total population sampling technique, involving all student-athletes within the selected group. By including the entire population of student-athletes, the research aims to determine how they manage their time effectively while balancing academic and athletic commitments. The research was conducted within the 2nd semester of academic year 2024–2025, allowing sufficient time for data collection and analysis.

This study has certain limitations. The findings are limited to a single institution, which may not fully represent the experiences of student-athletes from other schools. Since the data relies on self-reported survey responses, there is a possibility of response bias, where participants may provide socially desirable answers instead of completely accurate reflections of their experiences. Another limitation is the potential for a small sample size, which may affect the generalizability of the findings. The time constraints may limit the depth of data collection, as the study will rely on surveys rather than more

comprehensive methods like interviews or observations. To address these limitations, the study emphasized participant confidentiality to encourage honest responses. Future research may expand the scope by including multiple institutions, using a larger sample size, and incorporating qualitative methods to gain a more in-depth understanding of student-athletes' time management strategies.

RESULTS and DISCUSSION

Part I. Effective Time Management Strategies among Student-Athletes

Table 1
Effective Time Management Strategies Among Student Athletes in terms of Scheduling and Planning

No	Indicators	WAM	Verbal Interpretation
1	I usually make a clear and detailed plan to stay on top of both my schoolwork and sports activities.	3.77	Strongly Agree
2	I dedicate specific times for studying, training, and relaxing so I can balance everything better.	3.73	Strongly Agree
4	I prepare in advance for exams, games, and assignments to avoid last-minute stress.	3.63	Strongly Agree
5	I regularly look over my schedule and make changes when unexpected things come up.	3.60	Strongly Agree
3	I use tools like planners, calendars, or apps to help me stay organized and manage my daily and weekly responsibilities.	3.20	Agree
Average Weighted Arithmetic Mean		3.59	Strongly Agree

Note. The WAM for weighted arithmetic mean were used to interpret the survey responses. In this context, the range of 1.00 - 1.74 indicates Strongly Disagree, the range of 1.75 - 2.49 indicates Disagree, the range of 2.50 - 3.24 indicates Agree, 3.25 -4.00 indicates Strongly Agree.

Table 1 presents the effective time management strategies of student-athletes in terms of scheduling and planning. The statement with the highest weighted arithmetic mean was statement number one (1), "I usually make a clear and detailed plan to stay on top of both my schoolwork and sports activities", with a WAM of 3.77. The statement with the lowest WAM was statement number three (3), "I use tools like planners, calendars, or apps to help me stay organized and manage my daily and weekly responsibilities," with a WAM of 3.20. The average WAM for this indicator is 3.59, interpreted as Strongly Agree.

The data explicitly shows that student-athletes place a high value on detailed planning as a fundamental strategy to cope with the demands of both academics and athletics. They tend to prepare in advance and designate time for studying, training, and

resting. However, the relatively lower score for using planning tools suggests that many student-athletes rely more on traditional methods, such as handwritten notes or mental reminders, rather than integrating digital planning applications into their routines. This may reflect either a lack of familiarity with such tools or limited institutional promotion of these aids. From the researchers' point of view, training sessions on using digital time management applications could further optimize how student-athletes allocate their time.

This result supports the findings of Quimbo (2023), who noted that student-athletes who use structured planning tools such as the Eisenhower Matrix are more effective in balancing dual commitments. Similarly, Lohmer and Lasch (2020) emphasized that strategic planning and schedule adjustments are vital in settings that require handling multiple demands simultaneously, an insight that resonates with the practices of the respondents in this study.

Table 2
Effective Time Management Strategies Among Student Athletes in terms of Task Prioritization

No	Indicators	WAM	Verbal Interpretation
2	I manage my time between academics and athletics based on what's most urgent and important.	3.73	Strongly Agree
1	I focus on finishing the most important school and sports-related tasks before anything else.	3.67	Strongly Agree
4	When my academic and athletic schedules overlap, I know how to set clear priorities.	3.60	Strongly Agree
5	I feel confident in deciding which tasks need my immediate attention and which can wait.	3.60	Strongly Agree
3	I avoid putting things off by breaking big tasks into smaller, easier steps.	3.57	Strongly Agree
Average Weighted Arithmetic Mean		3.63	Strongly Agree

Note. The WAM for weighted arithmetic mean were used to interpret the survey responses. In this context, the range of 1.00 - 1.74 indicates Strongly Disagree, the range of 1.75 - 2.49 indicates Disagree, the range of 2.50 - 3.24 indicates Agree, 3.25 - 4.00 indicates Strongly Agree.

The statement with the highest weighted arithmetic mean was statement number two (2), "I manage my time between academics and athletics based on what's most urgent and important," with a WAM of 3.73. The lowest WAM was from statement number three (3), "I avoid putting things off by breaking big tasks into smaller, easier steps," with a WAM of 3.57. The overall WAM for this category is 3.63, interpreted as Strongly Agree.

The data explicitly shows that student-athletes are generally confident in identifying and prioritizing urgent academic and athletic responsibilities. Most of them

follow a hierarchy of importance and urgency in their daily routines, which helps them manage overlapping tasks more effectively. However, the slightly lower rating for breaking big tasks into smaller steps suggests that some student-athletes may still struggle with complex or time-consuming assignments, which can lead to delays or stress. From the researchers' point of view, equipping student-athletes with training on micro-tasking and incremental planning could further enhance productivity and reduce procrastination, especially during peak academic or competition periods.

These results are consistent with Guo et al. (2018), who discussed the importance of prioritizing critical tasks to improve productivity. Fortuna et al. (2024) also found that athletes who are able to prioritize tasks effectively show better academic performance, as they are better equipped to meet deadlines and perform well in both areas of their lives.

Table 3
Effective Time Management Strategies Among Student Athletes in terms of Goal Setting

No	Indicators	WAM	Verbal Interpretation
5	I take time to think about my successes and challenges so I can set better goals in the future.	3.77	Strongly Agree
1	I set clear, realistic goals for both my schoolwork and my athletic performance.	3.70	Strongly Agree
3	I adjust my goals when I see that my academic or athletic performance needs improvement.	3.60	Strongly Agree
4	Staying motivated is easier for me when I connect my daily efforts to my bigger life goals.	3.60	Strongly Agree
2	I regularly check my progress toward my short-term and long-term goals.	3.53	Strongly Agree
Average Weighted Arithmetic Mean		3.64	Strongly Agree

Note. The WAM for weighted arithmetic mean were used to interpret the survey responses. In this context, the range of 1.00 - 1.74 indicates Strongly Disagree, the range of 1.75 - 2.49 indicates Disagree, the range of 2.50 - 3.24 indicates Agree, 3.25 - 4.00 indicates Strongly Agree.

Table 3 outlines the goal-setting of student-athletes. Statement number five (5) with the highest WAM was 3.77, "I take time to think about my successes and challenges so I can set better goals in the future, while statement number two (2) had the lowest WAM of 3.53 for "I regularly check my progress toward my short-term and long-term goals." The average WAM of 3.64 reflects strong agreement overall.

The data explicitly shows that student-athletes highly value goal setting as a key motivational strategy. With a WAM of 3.77, they reflect on past achievements and

challenges to improve future goals. However, the lower score (3.53) in regularly checking progress suggests a gap between setting goals and maintaining accountability. From the researchers' point of view, this gap could hinder long-term development, especially in highly demanding seasons. There's a need to emphasize reflective practices and progress-tracking mechanisms such as journals, progress dashboards, or mentor check-ins, which would help sustain motivation and ensure that goals remain realistic and adaptable.

Höpfner and Keith (2021) warned that failing to meet overly ambitious goals may lower motivation, self-esteem, and affective outcomes. This is critical for student-athletes, who are already managing dual pressures. Mancera et al. (2024) added that realistic achievement goals improve quality of life and performance. Our findings echo this: student-athletes are goal-oriented, but without consistent reflection and recalibration, the benefits of goal-setting may not be fully realized. Educators and coaches should consider implementing regular review systems to support student-athletes in maintaining a balanced and sustainable goal trajectory.

Part II. Challenges in Time Management Strategies Faced by among Student-Athletes in Managing Academics and Athletics

Table 4
Challenges in Time Management Strategies faced by Student Athletes in terms of Academic Workload and Deadlines

No	Indicators	WAM	Verbal Interpretation
4	I experience stress due to overlapping deadlines for schoolwork and training schedules.	3.30	Strongly Agree
3	I often have to sacrifice sleep to meet both academic and athletic demands.	3.20	Agree
2	I find it difficult to focus on my studies after exhausting athletic training sessions.	2.90	Agree
1	I struggle to complete academic requirements on time due to my sports commitments.	2.83	Agree
5	I have difficulty balancing studying for exams and submitting academic projects while maintaining my athletic responsibilities.	2.83	Agree
Average Weighted Arithmetic Mean		3.01	Agree

Note. The WAM for weighted arithmetic mean were used to interpret the survey responses. In this context, the range of 1.00 - 1.74 indicates Strongly Disagree, the range of 1.75 - 2.49 indicates Disagree, the range of 2.50 - 3.24 indicates Agree, 3.25 -4.00 indicates Strongly Agree.

Table 4 shows the academic workload and deadlines challenges faced by student-athletes. The statement number four (4) had the highest WAM was 3.30 for "I

experience stress due to overlapping deadlines for schoolwork and training schedules," while the statement number five (5) had the lowest WAM of 2., "I have difficulty balancing studying for exams and submitting academic projects while maintaining my athletic responsibilities.". The average WAM is 3.01, indicating that academic stress is a common concern.

The data explicitly shows that overlapping deadlines between academics and athletics significantly contribute to student stress, with the highest WAM (3.30) reflecting this pressure. The respondents also indicated moderate challenges in maintaining sleep and managing academic focus. From the researchers' perspective, this demonstrates the need for a more flexible and responsive academic system that considers the unique pressures of student-athletes. If schools can introduce customizable deadlines or learning accommodations during peak sports seasons, academic integrity and mental wellness may both be preserved.

Hills and Peacock (2022) found that flexible academic extensions decrease stress and foster self-regulated learning. Likewise, Hextrum (2018) criticized academic systems for expecting student-athletes to resolve time conflicts on their own, leading to inequity. Our findings reinforce the idea that institutional reforms like flexible academic scheduling or athletic-adjusted academic modules are critical in addressing the unique demands placed on student-athletes.

Table 5
Challenges in Time Management Strategies faced by Student Athletes in terms of Athletic Training and Competition Schedules

No	Indicators	WAM	Verbal Interpretation
1	My training and competition schedules frequently interfere with my study time.	3.30	Strongly Agree
3	I struggle to attend review sessions or group studies due to sports commitments.	3.23	Agree
2	I feel physically and mentally exhausted after training, making it hard to concentrate on academic tasks.	3.17	Agree
4	I miss important academic discussions or classes because of training or competition.	3.07	Agree
5	My athletic commitments make it challenging to participate in academic-related extracurricular activities.	3.07	Agree
Average Weighted Arithmetic Mean		3.17	Agree

Note. The WAM for weighted arithmetic mean were used to interpret the survey responses. In this context, the range of 1.00 - 1.74 indicates Strongly Disagree, the range of 1.75 - 2.49 indicates Disagree, the range of 2.50 - 3.24 indicates Agree, 3.25 - 4.00 indicates Strongly Agree

Table 5 on the next page highlights the impact of training schedules on academic performance. Statement number one (1) had the highest WAM of 3.30, "My training and competition schedules frequently interfere with my study time," while statement number five (5) had the lowest WAM of 3.07, "My athletic commitments make it challenging to participate in academic-related extracurricular activities." The average WAM is 3.17.

The data explicitly shows that athletic commitments frequently clash with academic activities, with a WAM of 3.30 indicating that training often interferes with study time. The physical and mental exhaustion reported by students (WAM 3.17) implies a direct impact on academic concentration. The researchers believe that schools should implement collaborative academic-athletic calendars, where both coaches and teachers align major training dates and academic deadlines. Additionally, wellness programs focusing on recovery and mental resilience would benefit student-athletes during peak competition periods.

Liu and Taresh (2024) highlighted the dual-track development model, which helps athletes switch between training and academics without burnout. Ucan (2024) similarly noted that unbalanced sports schedules can lead to emotional and academic fatigue. Our findings affirm that the dual demands on student-athletes cannot be addressed by time management training alone—systemic alignment and support are essential.

Table 6
Challenges in Time Management Strategies faced by Student Athletes in terms of Time Conflicts between Academics and Athletics

No	Indicators	WAM	Verbal Interpretation
1	I often have to choose between attending classes and participating in sports events.	3.07	Agree
4	I feel overwhelmed when academic deadlines coincide with major competitions.	3.07	Agree
5	I sometimes prioritize one over the other, leading to guilt or dissatisfaction in either academics or athletics.	2.90	Agree
2	I struggle to maintain a structured daily schedule that accommodates both academics and athletics.	2.73	Agree
3	I find it hard to communicate with teachers and coaches when conflicts arise between my academic and athletic commitments.	2.70	Agree
Average Weighted Arithmetic Mean		2.89	Agree

Note. The WAM for weighted arithmetic mean were used to interpret the survey responses. In this context, the range of 1.00 - 1.74 indicates Strongly Disagree, the range of 1.75 - 2.49 indicates Disagree, the range of 2.50 - 3.24 indicates Agree, 3.25 - 4.00 indicates Strongly Agree.

Table 6 discusses the conflicts faced by student-athletes when academic and athletic responsibilities overlap. The statement number one (1) had the highest WAM of 3.07, "I often have to choose between attending classes and participating in sports events", while the statement number three (3) had the lowest WAM of 2, "I find it hard to communicate with teachers and coaches when conflicts arise between my academic and athletic commitments.". The average WAM was 2.89.

The data explicitly shows that student-athletes are frequently forced to choose between academics and sports, especially when major events conflict with exams or deadlines. The WAM of 3.07 for these items confirms the emotional and practical burden of such decisions. What stands out most is the low score (2.70) on their ability to communicate these conflicts with authority figures. The researchers view this as a critical barrier: without open dialogue and institutional mechanisms for resolution, student-athletes will continue to suffer in silence and underperform in one area or another.

Sun et al. (2023) found that time conflicts negatively impact life satisfaction and emotional well-being in athletes. Owen (2016) added that time management interventions alone are insufficient; communication gaps must also be addressed. Our findings align with these conclusions, highlighting the urgent need for structured communication protocols between students, teachers, and coaches to ensure academic-athletic balance and mental well-being.

Part III. Output of the Study

The main output of this study is an informational brochure titled "Smart Time Management Strategies: A Student-Athlete's Guide to Effective Time Management." This brochure was developed as a practical and visually engaging tool to guide student-athletes in managing their time effectively. It outlines key strategies such as setting priorities, avoiding procrastination, creating routines, and using downtime wisely. It also offers clear recommendations like using planners, setting SMART goals, and seeking support from mentors and peers. The brochure integrates both academic and athletic perspectives, presenting tips that are easy to understand and apply in daily routines.

The brochure reflects the study's findings that student-athletes benefit significantly from structured and intentional time management practices. The inclusion of strategies, recommendations, and a motivational conclusion shows that when student-athletes are equipped with the right tools and knowledge, they can take control of their responsibilities without feeling overwhelmed. The visual presentation and student-friendly language enhance the accessibility and effectiveness of the material, making it an appropriate output for the intended audience.

This output is significant it provides a user-friendly and cost-effective solution that can be immediately implemented in schools. The brochure serves as a practical guide for student-athletes to apply what they've learned from the study. It supports their day-to-day routines, encourages accountability, and reinforces the importance of balance between academics and athletics. Moreover, it demonstrates the school's commitment to student well-being and holistic development, promoting a culture that values both

academic success and athletic excellence.

Conclusions

After analyzing the data, the researchers arrived at the following conclusions.

1. For most of the respondents, the most effective time management strategies commonly used to balance their academic and athletic performance is goal setting.
2. In terms of challenges in time management strategies, the respondents found athletic training and competition schedules the most challenging.
3. The researchers suggested an informational brochure to enhance the effectiveness and minimize the challenges in balancing academic and athletic responsibilities of the respondents.

Recommendations

Based on the conclusions drawn from the study, the following recommendations are proposed:

1. Academic institutions may develop structured academic support programs specifically designed for student-athletes, such as flexible scheduling, academic advising, and time management workshops.
2. Coaches and athletic administrators may coordinate with academic departments to minimize schedule conflicts and promote a balanced approach to training and academic responsibilities.
3. Student-athletes may be encouraged to continuously refine their time management practices, particularly in prioritization and planning, to better cope with academic and athletic demands.
4. Future researchers may conduct similar studies using larger samples, different research designs, or qualitative approaches to gain deeper insights into the experiences of student-athletes and the factors affecting their time management practices.

Compliance with Ethical Standards

The authors declare that this study complied with ethical research standards. Informed consent was obtained from all respondents prior to their participation, and participation was voluntary with the right to withdraw at any time. The anonymity and confidentiality of the respondents were strictly maintained, and data privacy protocols were observed throughout the study. The well-being of the respondents was safeguarded, and no conflict of interest existed in the conduct of the research. Plagiarism was strictly avoided, and there was no bias in the interpretation of the findings. The results of the study were used solely for academic and research purposes. Any use of artificial intelligence tools was limited to language editing and formatting assistance, with full responsibility for the content retained by the authors.

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